

A Sociological Evaluation of Public Participation in the Implementation of the Smart City Mission: A Case Study of Aurangabad Smart City

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Abstract:

This study critically examines the nature and extent of citizen participation in the implementation of the Smart City Mission in Aurangabad (Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar), Maharashtra. Using a qualitative methodology and grounded in the theoretical framework of neoliberal urbanism, the research explores whether public involvement is genuinely integrated into urban governance or remains largely symbolic. Data were collected through semi-structured interviews with 50 corporates, analysis of policy documents, RTI responses, and secondary reports. Findings reveal a dominance of bureaucratic decision-making, limited inclusion of elected representatives and citizens, and a clear gap between the mission's stated vision of participatory governance and its practical execution. The study highlights how centralized, technocratic governance under the Smart City framework often undermines democratic engagement, suggesting a need for more inclusive, citizen-driven approaches to urban development.

Keywords: Smart City Mission Citizen Participation Neoliberal Urbanism Urban Governance, Aurangabad Smart City.

1. Introduction:

The Smart Cities Mission (SCM), launched on 25 June 2015 by Prime Minister Narendra Modi, aims to enhance the quality of urban life in 100 selected Indian cities. The initiative is designed to promote efficient service delivery, robust infrastructure, economic development, and inclusive urban transformation. It is structured around four key pillars: social, economic, physical, and institutional development. A core objective of the mission is to ensure meaningful citizen participation, where citizens are actively involved in decision-making processes, not merely engaged in ceremonial or symbolic roles. This paper specifically focuses on the case of Aurangabad

Smart City (now Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar), with the following section providing an overview of its institutional and developmental profile under the Smart City framework

1.2 Aurangabad Smart City Development Corporation Limited (ASCDCL):

The Aurangabad Smart City Development Corporation Limited (ASCDCL) is a Special Purpose Vehicle (SPV) established under Section 8 of the Companies Act, 2013. It was incorporated in September 2016, following the selection of Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar (formerly Aurangabad) in Round 2 of the Smart City Mission Challenge. ASCDCL was created to implement and manage the Smart City project for the city. ASCDCL is jointly owned by the Government of Maharashtra and the Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar Municipal Corporation. As the nodal agency, it is responsible for planning, coordinating, and executing various smart city initiatives aimed at improving urban infrastructure and services. (Source: Aurangabad Smart City Official Website)

1.3 Vision Statement of ASCDCL:

"To create a clean and green city that is lovable, with its rich cultural and natural heritage fabric seamlessly interwoven with technology and intelligence, providing an affordable, safe, and high-quality urban life that is socially inclusive." (Source: Aurangabad Smart City Official Website).

Dameri (2014) highlights that smart cities often fail to meet their goals due to neglecting citizens' needs and imposing one-size-fits-all technological solutions. This research critically examines social inclusion in the Aurangabad Smart City Mission by assessing the level of citizen participation. It adopts Hollands' (2015) neoliberal urbanism framework, which critiques smart cities for favoring technocratic and corporate interests over democratic involvement and inclusivity.

1.4 Theoretical Framework:

Neoliberal urbanism, as discussed by Hollands (2015), frames smart cities as spaces driven by corporate interests, emphasizing technology and efficiency over social inclusion and grassroots engagement. This model often results in governance structures that prioritize profit and commodify urban life, sidelining democratic practices and reducing citizens to passive recipients of pre-designed solutions. The notion of *smartmentality* reflects this passive role, where public participation becomes tokenistic used to legitimize top-down agendas rather than fostering genuine decision-making. This framework is essential for critically assessing the Aurangabad Smart City Mission, especially in examining whether citizen involvement is substantive or merely symbolic. Specifically addressing the research question- *To what extent is citizen participation in the Aurangabad Smart City Mission genuinely integrated into urban governance, or is it merely symbolic within the framework of neoliberal urbanism?*

1.5 Research Methodology:

This research employs a qualitative methodology to capture the depth and complexity of citizen experiences, official narratives, and institutional practices related to urban governance and participation.

1.5.1 Data Sources:

A. Primary Data

- **Semi-Structured Interviews:** Elected local representatives (corporates)
- **Field Observations:** Participation in Smart City public consultations, events, and digital platforms

B. Secondary Data:

- Government and policy documents (Smart City Mission Guidelines, ASCDCL progress reports)
- Reports from Parliamentary Committees and urban development bodies (e.g., 2024 Standing Committee Report)
- RTI responses

1.5.2 Sampling Strategy:

A total of 50 corporates were purposively selected for semi-structured interviews, as they represent citizens in the urban governance structure and act as key intermediaries in the Smart City implementation process.

1.6 Data Analysis:

3. Do you think the participation of citizens in Smart City projects is meaningful and influential in decision-making?

4. Are citizens in your ward actively involved in Smart City planning and implementation?

1.6.2 Analysis from the Reports:

The report titled “*Engaging With Maharashtra’s Smart City Program: The Way Forward*” by Habitat Forum (INHAF), produced under the Smart City Coalition initiated by INHAF, offers critical insights into the functioning of the Smart City program in Aurangabad.

In the case of Aurangabad, interviews with Members of the Legislative Assembly (MLAs) revealed that both MLAs and Members of Parliament (MPs) were excluded from the proposal preparation process. Their involvement was perceived as an infringement upon the jurisdiction of the municipal corporation. Additionally, several interviewees pointed out that citizens were not adequately consulted or taken into confidence during the planning phase. As a result, the

bureaucracy emerged as the dominant decision-making authority, sidelining both elected representatives and the citizens at large.

1.6.3 RTI Responses:

Analysis of Advisory Forum Meetings (RTI Ref. No: ASCDCL/2025/31, Dated 13.01.2025):

According to the Smart City Mission Guidelines (Clause 13.3, p. 17), each city is required to establish a City Level Advisory Forum (CLAF) and convene its meetings periodically to ensure meaningful citizen participation and stakeholder engagement. The CLAF is intended to facilitate collaboration among elected representatives, government officials, civil society, local institutions, and private actors in the planning and monitoring of Smart City projects.

However, as revealed through an RTI response (Ref. No: ASCDCL/2025/31), only **02 meetings** of the CLAF have been conducted in Aurangabad since its inception in 2016. This limited engagement raises concerns about the actual implementation of participatory governance as envisioned in the mission guidelines.

1.7 Key Findings:

1. Impact of Neoliberal Governance Structures:

The findings indicate a clear dominance of bureaucratic control in the implementation of the Smart City Mission, with limited involvement of elected representatives and citizens. This reflects a neoliberal model of urban governance, where decision-making is centralized, technocratic, and efficiency-driven. As a result, democratic engagement is weakened, and the goals of social inclusion are sidelined.

2. Gap Between Policy Vision and Practice:

Despite the Smart City Mission's stated commitment to citizen participation and inclusive governance, the actual implementation reveals a significant disconnect. For instance, as per RTI data, only two meetings of the City Level Advisory Forum (CLAF) have been held since 2016. This points to a largely symbolic engagement with citizens, contradicting the participatory ideals outlined in the mission guidelines.

1.8 Limitations:

This study is limited to the case of the Aurangabad Smart City, with data collected from 50 respondents. Furthermore, restricted access to internal government documents and the possibility of respondent bias may have constrained the depth and scope of the analysis.

1.9 Conclusion:

This study provides a critical sociological evaluation of citizen participation in the implementation of the Smart City Mission in Aurangabad, highlighting significant gaps between the mission's policy vision and its actual practice. Although the Smart Cities Mission emphasizes inclusive and participatory governance, the findings reveal that citizen engagement remains largely symbolic. The dominance of technocratic decision-making through the ASCDCL, limited involvement of elected representatives, and the negligible number of City Level Advisory Forum meetings since 2016 illustrate the constraints of neoliberal urban governance. Through interviews with 50 cooperators and analysis of policy documents and RTI responses, the study demonstrates how participatory mechanisms are often sidelined in favor of efficiency-oriented, top-down planning. This reflects a broader trend where smart city development risks becoming disconnected from the democratic needs and lived realities of urban residents.

For the Smart Cities Mission to achieve its stated goals of social inclusion and sustainable urban transformation there is an urgent need to institutionalize genuine citizen participation, ensure transparency in governance processes, and strengthen the role of elected representatives. Without such reforms, smart city initiatives may continue to reinforce existing exclusions rather than address them.

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